

Edwin Roy Watson.

Born July, 1880; Died November, 1926.

By BAWA KAHTAR SINGH.

Edwin Roy Watson, second son of William Watson and Emily Watson (née Bond) was educated at the Nottingham High School, where he held scholarships throughout his school career. He went up to Jesus College, Cambridge, in 1899 with the senior entrance scholarship. He obtained high Honours in the first part of the Natural Sciences Tripos in 1901 and in the second part in 1902. He spent two years (1902-04) in post-graduate research in chemistry at Cambridge under the guidance of Dr. S. Ruhemann. He came out to India in 1904 as Professor of Chemistry at the Sibpur Engineering College, Bengal. After about two years' work there, he was transferred to Dacca College, Dacca, in a similar capacity where he worked till 1921. He was then transferred to Cawnpore as Principal of the newly established Government Technological Institute. He was overworked during the latter part of his service and consequently suffered from a nervous breakdown, which necessitated his taking leave out of India last April. He consulted some nerve specialists in Switzerland, but finding no relief there, he returned to London. He did not recover from mental depression, and died in November 1926, under circumstances of peculiar sadness, at the early age of forty six.

Watson took a very prominent part in the development of higher chemical teaching in this country, and the object of this note is to describe some of his contributions to chemical science. Besides being a very able and attractive lecturer in chemistry, he prosecuted research very vigorously both himself and with the help of his advanced students.

Watson published three papers in 1904 at Cambridge, two of them jointly with Dr. Ruhemann and the third independently. The first of these papers (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1904, 85, 456) dealt with the preparation of ketones of the acetylene series with a view to see whether they are transformed by the action of bases into heterocyclic compounds similar to those formed from the esters of the acetylene series (Ruhemann and Stapleton, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1900, 77, 289).

In the second paper (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1904, 86, 1170) it was shown that unsaturated olefinic ketonic compounds form addition

products with organic bases and that these additive compounds which are first formed, subsequently undergo further changes.

In the third paper (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1904, 85, 1819) Watson showed that the action of bases on acetylenic ketones is to form additive compounds by the addition of the base to the carbon atoms of the acetylenic linking. This behaviour is analogous to the addition of bases to olefinic ketonic compounds. This research had also as its object the preparation of acetylenic ketones.

On his arrival in India, Watson made a break with the above type of research, and started on an entirely new line. He studied (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1906, 89, 578) the electrolysis of silver nitrate by altering the current-concentration and density and also the strength of the solution. He found that the anodic product in all cases was silver peroxynitrate Ag_2NO_3 . The decomposition of this compound with boiling water was shown to take place according to the following equation:

One of the products of this decomposition was silver dioxide which was claimed to have been obtained pure for the first time.

From 1909 to 1922 Watson published about thirty papers, either alone or in collaboration with his pupils, on the chemistry of dyes. It will be thus seen that he again returned to organic chemistry, but cultivated an entirely different subject from that with which he was associated at Cambridge. In this respect he proves himself to be at once original and very resourceful.

His earlier studies in this branch related to testing the fastness of dyes of the polyhydroxy-benzophenone series (*J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1911, 30, 196). He established that an increase in the number of hydroxyl groups tends to diminish the fastness to light, with the exception of the 2:3:4-trihydroxy compound. Most of these dyes are brightened and deepened by treatment with alkali, and the xanthenes are not so fast to acid or light as the polyhydroxybenzophenones. This subject was further studied in a later paper (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1912, 101, 1238).

In another communication (*J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1911, 30, 6) it was shown that benzene-azo-salicylic acid, when dyed with a chrome mordant, is characterized by a fastness towards light, alkali and acid superior to that of any other simple mono-azo dye. Attempts to prepare similar dyes (*ibid.*, 1912, 31, 968) having the same all round fastness, but of a deeper colour, by replacing the phenyl

group with heavier hydrocarbon residues, or with other groups containing chromophores, and also by substituting α -hydroxy-naphthoic acid residue for that of salicylic acid, met with only partial success.

Since many azo-dyes of not more complicated structure possess the desired shades, a number of well-known azo-dyes prepared from naphthol sulphonic acids were examined (*ibid*, 1913, 32, 642), from which it was concluded that the relative position of the hydroxyl- and chromophore groups is the determining factor in the colour of the dye, the ortho-position favouring red, violet, and blue shades, and the para-position giving brown shades.

In 1912-13, Watson's attention was drawn to the insect *Cydnus Indicus* (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1913, 103, 548). At Dacca this insect is attracted to lights, often in large number in the nights of June and the following rainy months. It is notorious on account of its strong and unpleasant odour. It is known in Bengali as *gandi*. It is also known as *geranium-bug* and belongs to the *Heteroptera*. Maxwell-Lefroy ("Indian Insect Life") remarks that "a feature of the great majority of Heteroptera is the aromatic odour they protect themselves with. This odour is due to the secretion by special glands of an oily fluid, which is excreted at will from the odiferous orifices and rapidly volatilises." Watson found that the strong and disagreeable odour of *Cydnus Indicus* is due to cycloheptane carboxylic acid which is present in the insects to the extent of 1½ per cent., and another substance ($C_{11}H_{20}O$, ?) present in much smaller quantity (0.1—0.2 per cent.). The intensity of the odour of the latter substance can be judged from the fact that each insect contains 0.000005 gram of it, and yet one insect is sufficient to scent the whole room.

Watson's interest in dye-chemistry was not confined only to the production of dyes of tinctorial value. He put forward a very remarkable theory on the relation between chemical constitution and depth of colour of dyes (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1914, 105, 759). According to this theory those dyes which are quinonoid in all possible tautomeric forms exhibit a deep colour, however simple the molecule may be. On the other hand, if there is the possibility of the molecule existing in a non-quinonoid form, it may not attain a deep colour, although, the molecular complexity may be very considerable. A survey of all the better known dyestuffs fully bears out this theory, and it explains remarkable differences in depths of colour between dyes of very similar constitution. A permanent

quinonoid structure alone is not sufficient, for example dihydroxy-*p*-benzoquinone ; the substance must be capable of tautomerising from one quinonoid arrangement to another. The theory has been fully borne out by the preparation of dyes of deep colour from quercetin (see below).

The quest for the ultimate cause of colour has led to the production of a great mass of literature on the theoretical side of the subject by a number of chemists. Its scientific interest and its practical utility led Watson to throw himself enthusiastically into this line of research. In 1917 Watson gave a course of lectures on "Colour and Constitution" at the University of Leeds. These lectures were published in the following year in the series of Monographs on Industrial Chemistry edited by Sir Edward Thorpe (Longmans Green & Co.) and show the great mastery of the subject possessed by Watson.

During the years 1911-15, Watson was engaged in the study of dyes of the flavone group. In the first paper of the series (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1914, 105, 386) experiments were described which had as their object the introduction of an additional hydroxyl group into the quercetin molecule. By the methods employed, however, this could not be effected, because it was found impossible to convert amino-quercetin pentamethyl ether by means of the diazo-compound into the corresponding hydroxy-derivative. On the other hand, amino-quercetin was successfully prepared and it was shown that the amino group exerted but little effect on the tinctorial property of the dye.

With the same object in view, namely, to deepen the colour of the dye and to prepare new polyhydroxy flavones which might prove of future service in the study of the natural members of the group, identical methods were applied to both luteolin and morin (Perkin and Watson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1915, 107, 198). Luteolin and morin after being converted into their ethers were nitrated and the nitro groups reduced to amino groups. As in the case of the analogous quercetin compound, attempts to displace the amino group by hydroxyl in amino-morin-pentamethyl ether failed. The influence of the new auxochromes was studied spectroscopically, and it was found that a multiplication of auxochromic groups resulted in a widening of the principal absorption band, and a slight shift in its position towards the red end of the spectrum. The effect on the second band which lies in the violet and ultraviolet was apparent in the spectroscope, but alteration in this band had little influence on the visible colour of the substance. It was established that

whereas an increase of auxochromes deepens the colour very considerably in certain groups of dyes, as is shown in the difference between alizarine, and alizarine blue W. R., and fluorescein and gallein, in other cases, such as flavone group, a similar multiplication of auxochromes has very little effect on the colour.

The foregoing methods having failed to produce deeper-coloured dyes, various other attempts were carried out (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1914, 105, 389; 1915, 170, 1477). 6'-Nitroquercetin pentamethyl ether was partly demethylated, yielding 6'-nitroquercetin dimethyl ether but this was found to be useless for dyeing purposes. Various attempts to introduce additional auxochromes failed, and the multiplication of chromophoric groups in the molecule also gave rise to unsatisfactory results. Success was obtained in another way. The objective sought was to introduce into the molecule some substituent which would produce a permanent quinonoid structure, and this was gained by replacing the pyrone ketonic radicle by the group—CR·OH. The new compounds of this type might be expected to resemble in behaviour the dyes of the triphenyl carbinol series. Compounds of the following structure (I and II) were, therefore, prepared by the action of Grignard's reagent on quercetin pentaethyl ether and subsequent de-ethylation with hydriodic acid. The base corresponding with II dyes wool violet or crimson, according as to whether alum or tin is used.

This series of compounds possesses considerable interest in connection with the colour of flowers, fruits, etc. Willstätter's work

(Willstätter and Mallison, *Sitzungsber. K. Akad. Wiss.*, Berlin, 1914, 769) has shown that these natural colouring matters are very closely related to the compounds obtained by Watson and his pupils and possess very similar properties.

Other studies by Watson related to the preparation of dyes from phenanthraquinone (*J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1915, 34, 1186; *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, 119, 1211) and of sulphide dyes (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1920, 117, 830; 1922, 121, 1939, 2414).

In 1921, Watson was selected as Principal of the newly established Technological Institute at Cawnpore by the Government of the United Provinces. Watson threw himself, with his usual enthusiasm, into the organisation of this new Institute. He took a very considerable part in teaching and carried out a good deal of research work in technological subjects, some of which is published in the *Journal of our Society*. He was forced to abandon his chemical studies on dyes on account of the nature of his new duties—a circumstance which he much regretted. This divorce from his former scientific studies was keenly felt by him and coupled with his heavy duties at Cawnpore hastened his tragic and premature death. At Dacca also he worked very hard and spent about ten hours daily in the laboratory and trained a band of students in research, who are now serving as successful teachers of chemistry in different parts of the country. His simple and straightforward manner greatly endeared him to his students and colleagues.

Watson received the degree of Doctor of Science of the University of London in 1913. He was President of the Chemistry Section of the Indian Science Congress held at Bangalore in 1924 and gave a very illuminating and interesting address on the organisation, direction and stimulation of chemical research (*Proc. Eleventh Ind. Sci. Congress*, 1924, 68). He was a Vice-President of the Indian Chemical Society, the inception of which owes much to him.

Watson married Lily Mary Hurtston, of Leamington Spa at St. George's Cathedral, Madras, in October, 1908, and had two children who died in infancy. One of his brothers, Harold Argyll Watson, of the Indian Civil Service, is at present serving in the Madras Presidency. Watson's main recreation was painting and he had exhibited with success at Simla, Naini Tal, and other fine arts exhibitions.

His death is a very great loss to our Society in particular and to Chemical Science in general. He leaves numerous friends both in this country and in England to mourn his loss.